

DEVELOPING STUDENTS' SPEECH THROUGH WORKING ON PROVERBS IN
PRIMARY EDUCATION

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Аннотация. В данной статье говорится о проблеме совершенствования речи учащихся младших классов путем чтения пословиц. Показаны методические аспекты развития речи учащихся на основе работы над пословицами.

Ключевые слова: начальное образование, фольклор, развитие речи, пословица, идея текста, переносное значение, работа над значением слова.

Abstract. This article talks about the issue of improving the speech of elementary school students by reading proverbs. It shows methodological aspects of developing students' speech based on working on proverbs.

Key words: primary education, folklore, speech development, proverb, text idea, figurative meaning, work on word meaning.

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, a long-term plan for national development has been developed, with education and upbringing defined as the practical foundation for its implementation. Raising the younger generation as individuals with high moral values does not occur on its own. This process must be formed in accordance with the requirements of the state and society in which they live, and is primarily achieved through the education and upbringing provided in primary school. A significant portion of the material taught in primary grades consists of works of folk oral literature. By studying them, students are taught to think independently and creatively, express thoughts clearly, understand lexemes and figurative language in texts, and develop the ability to use them freely in speech.

Through samples of folk oral creativity—especially proverbs—students are nurtured with a spirit of love for the homeland, respect for the people, and reverence for the language. Their communication culture is shaped, vocabulary enriched, and scope of thinking expanded.

Proverbs are short, often poetic, wise expressions born from life experience and reflecting the wisdom of the people. They cover a wide range of topics and life situations. Proverbs often contain advice or moral lessons, such as: “If you plow, plow in the fall; if not in the fall, then a hundred times,” or “A person without skills has no joy in work.”

As one of the most ancient forms of folk oral literature, proverbs use various artistic devices, including repetition of harmonious sounds. The immortal sayings of great masters of words with rich life and creative experience often resemble folk proverbs. For example, many wise expressions from Alisher Navoi’s *Mahbub ul-qulub* are similar in nature: “Learning drop by drop makes one wise; collected drop by drop, it becomes a river,” “Without control over the tongue—without respect from the people.” It is well known that working on literary texts in primary education is conducted step-by-step. These same stages must be considered when teaching proverbs.

Grades 1–2 represent the first stage of studying proverbs, with the literacy period being the preparatory phase for reading and learning proverbs.

Even during the literacy phase, students begin reading proverbs. The proverbs presented during the alphabet period are related to the content of the text and serve to concisely convey the idea of the text

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to students. At this stage, students are asked to read proverbs and explain them as much as they understand. The teacher supplements their responses and supports them with examples.

Teaching proverbs requires thorough preparation from the teacher. When preparing for each lesson, the teacher should plan how to organize exercises around a proverb that fits the content and idea of the text. It is advisable to include them in the lesson plan and use explanatory dictionaries (e.g., “Hikmatnoma” by Sh. Shomahmudov and Sh. Shorahmedov, an explanatory dictionary of Uzbek proverbs, Tashkent, 1990) to find simple explanations. Teachers should have access to proverb collections and related explanatory literature.

In primary grades, reading, learning, and analyzing proverbs given under texts should occur only after reading and analyzing the main text. It is difficult to explain the meaning of a proverb without understanding the author’s intended message. Authors themselves often explain proverbs through the events in their works.

In grades 1–2, emphasis is placed on expressive reading and memorization of proverbs. The first-grade textbook includes many questions and assignments focused on learning proverbs. For example, in the section “Etiquette is Beauty for Humans,” the task “Explain the meaning of the proverb ‘There is blessing in contentment’” is given, or after the “Spring—The World Blossoms” section, students are asked to recite proverbs about acquiring knowledge. Such assignments are aimed at learning specific proverbs.

Beyond learning and memorizing the meaning of proverbs in grades 1–2, students should also work on vocabulary exercises related to explanatory words and phrases, artistic devices, figurative meanings, opposites, and recurring words. For example, in the first-grade “Reading Literacy” textbook, the proverb “Your native land is your golden cradle” is given. While working on this proverb, questions such as “What other words can replace the word ‘land’?”, “What is the native land compared to in the proverb?”, “Can a cradle really be made of gold?” are posed to enrich students’ vocabulary and improve connected speech. Similarly, in explaining the proverb “If your country extends a hand to you, always be loyal to it,” students can be asked to provide examples from that section’s texts or from real-life state support provided for children. For instance, “The ‘Jar’ sports complex was created for your healthy development. You are receiving free education at school. So what should you do in return?” In working with the figurative language of this proverb, it’s useful to ask questions like “What do you understand by ‘extending a hand’?”

In primary grades, proverbs are used after studying texts to help reveal the message of the work and form conclusions. This helps unpack the meaning of the proverb. Activities with proverbs in grade 1 continue into grade 2. By working with proverbs, students come to understand their origins and how they differ from ordinary sentences.

In grade 1, attention is focused on proper reading and memorization of proverbs, while in grade 2, students may be asked to recite proverbs that match the content of a text.

In grades 3–4, proverbs are studied both in special lessons and during literary analysis. The purpose is to broaden students’ worldviews, develop skills for accurate and conscious reading, and enable full comprehension of each word and the overall meaning of the proverb. Students should be able to independently identify proverbs and wise sayings in the text and use them to draw correct conclusions about what they’ve read.

In grades 3–4, the topic of “Proverbs” is studied separately. Students are provided with basic information about the origins and creation of proverbs. They learn that proverbs emerged from long-

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term life experiences and are a tool of upbringing and moral development in every nation's cultural heritage.

Proverbs are taught by topic. For example, in the 4th-grade "Reading Literacy" textbook, proverbs are grouped under several themes. In teaching by themes, proverbs should be linked to relevant readings. The meaning and idea of a work should be connected with appropriate proverbs. Students should be encouraged to explain proverbs using real-life examples or to independently create stories that match the message of the proverb.

In grades 3–4, analytical work on the proverb genre is consistently carried out throughout the academic year. Assignments include: "State a proverb related to the idea of the work," "Create a crossword or rebus based on proverbs," and events such as "Proverb Recitation Contest" or "Proverb Debate" are held.

All the above confirms that proverbs are an important tool in developing students' speech. From this perspective, it is advisable to widely use the methodological possibilities of teaching proverbs to improve primary school students' speech. This highlights the importance of adhering to the principles of visibility, connection between theory and practice, and the unity of education and upbringing in teaching proverbs.

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